

Munir's Geogrometry Theory of Intolerance

Geogrometry¹ is a combination of Geo-Earth; Metry-Measurement; Geography-Location.

Intolerance is not inherently cyclical but rather a socio-cyclic complex phenomenon stemming from biased and prejudiced attitudes. The nature and intensity of intolerance can vary, making it challenging to measure.

Addressing intolerance requires more than just education and awareness about diversity and inclusivity. The complex interplay of personal identity, experiences, exposures, narratives, affiliations, hopes, desires, and expectations- all have a pivotal role in shaping our level of tolerance.

Munir's Geogrometry Theory of Intolerance states, "The seed of intolerance is deeply ingrained in personal, social, political, and familial factors that can trigger violence and intolerance in different forms and dimensions, at any time and place. The intensity with which it hits varies, and the number of times it evokes differs, but mostly this crypto-cyclic process remains in dormancy unless triggered."

The theory identifies identity conflict and ideological clashes as primary factors of intolerance. Vulnerable populations, such as the elderly, isolated youth, members of dysfunctional families, university students and teachers, introverts, and those affected by poverty, are mainly susceptible to the effects of intolerance.

¹ Intense glocal challenges with socio-cyclic implications